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Annotation: *Global competences are thinking and cognitive competences, interaction (social competences) and self-relational competences.*

Recently, the term "new literacy" appeared. This concept includes not only "what I know", but also "how I know". In other words, a person not only has knowledge, but also skillfully applies it in any situation.

Key words: *competence, reading literacy, PIRLS studies, focus, PISA.*

In order for a person to apply his knowledge, he must first master the basics of literacy, the functions of which are:

- reading literacy, because we get a lot of different information by reading texts, both on paper and on the screen of smartphones and computers.

- mathematical literacy. This is not only the ability to calculate, but also the ability to build a model, i.e. creating a vision of the future. Let's focus on the first component of core competencies.

Reading literacy is the measurable part of reading ability.

They began to measure reading literacy in the 20th and 21st centuries when it became clear that the world has changed, that the learning process lasts a lifetime, and that this process covers more and more areas of life.

Reading literacy is typically assessed at two key critical ages. For schoolchildren, it is at age 10 (PIRLS) - how schoolchildren read and understand texts, at age 15 (PISA) - it tests schoolchildren's mathematics, science and reading literacy.

The evaluation criteria will be different.

What is evaluated in PIRLS studies?

Two different readings:

- in order to gain literary experience;
- in order to use information in education and everyday life.

The study includes four groups of reading ability:

- find the specified information;
- forming conclusions;
- interpretation and synthesis of information;
- analysis and evaluation of text content, linguistic features and structure.

The measurement of reading literacy at the first age is related to the fact that the student who has reached this age has already been taught to read, i.e. the process of

learning to read is basically complete. Therefore, two types of reading are evaluated. First, knowledge, the range of interest in reading, accumulated experience, which includes not only fiction, but also non-fiction texts and non-fiction texts, and then fiction. Second, it determines how the student can use the acquired skills to master and apply them in the further education process and in his future life, because the social life of the student at this age begins to expand rapidly.

Four groups of reading skills are assessed.

The main, simplest - to find information in a certain form, i.e. you need to find information about the key word in the question or synthesize information from two sentences. For example, the first sentence reads: "Alexander Sergeevich Pushkin was born in Moscow." And after 3-4 sentences: "The great Russian poet was born in 1799." The question arises: "In what year was Alexander Sergeevich Pushkin born?"

In addition, an important skill is to draw conclusions. If a student achieves these two levels, it is considered that he can successfully study and develop his reading skills.

A high level of reading skills is the ability to interpret information and summarize it, analyze the text both in terms of content and structure.

The next age point is 15 years old, because at this age a person is determined by the further educational process and begins to actively use studies to exist in this world.

Reading literacy is a person's ability to understand, use, and think about written texts. This understanding is measured using test items.

With the help of special questionnaires, the ability to study is tested to be interesting, to achieve one's goals, to expand one's possibilities and to participate in social life. If reading is not part of a person's normal activity, then a person will never achieve a high level of reading literacy.

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